

A STUDY ON IMPULSIVE CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR AND ITS DETERMINANTS

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Abstract:

Impulse buying is an emerging phenomenon, which has been the focus of the retailers to attract the customers. Impulse behaviour is the outcome of emotional reactions that generate unpredicted urge to buy. Consumer behaviour is nowadays gaining much importance for retailers. Due to expansion of organized retail in India, retailers are trying to understand the behaviour of consumers that what product the consumer seeks for, why they need a particular product, when they need it and how they are going to purchase a product. Earlier there was a traditional buying behaviour of consumer in which they make a list for purchasing a product and they went to a particular store and purchase it. But now the whole buying behaviour is changing due to rise in the income level, i.e. increase in purchasing power of consumer, change in the socio-cultural environment, change in lifestyle and consumption pattern of consumers etc. This influences the consumer to act in irrational manner which is known as unplanned buying. So the present study will aim to know about impulse buying, its types and various factors influencing impulse buying. This paper tries to know how consumer's traditional planned shopping behaviour is shifting to impulse behaviour.

Key Words: Impulse Buying, Traditional Buying Behaviour & Purchase Behaviour

Introduction:

Stores sell hundreds and thousands of products daily and consumers are consuming these products at the cost of their income. It only depends on the income of the person, that how much and how many times he or she visits shopping stores to buy products. It is usually seen that buyers purchase products which they have not planned and this phenomenon of unplanned purchasing is termed as impulse buying. Impulsive purchasing, generally defined as a consumer's unplanned purchase which is an important part of buyer behaviour. Impulse buying is such a sudden phenomenon where instinct plays a predominant role. A customer makes a purchase without proper planning or prior homework. This is the scenario that marketer and retailer try to capitalize and harness. They provide such impulsive stimuli which are packaged innovatively clubbed with basic needs and wants. Sometimes customers are not able to express the selection of their brand and might not be aware of his internal decision making. But an unconscious decision making process takes place in his mind which is influenced by cognition and experience. Thus impulse buying behaviour is very much tune with the psychological and physiological need of the customer.

What Motivates Impulsive Buying?

Impulsive buying is a psychological phenomenon & the culture of consumption trigger buyers to succumb to temptation resulting them to buy anything without consideration of its consequences. Impulsive buying can be correlated to unhappiness & anxiety & is required to be controlled from psychological perspective. Impulsive buying tendency can be linked to personality trait which triggers a person making impulsive purchase a habit. Impulsive buyers are mainly social beings who are very much concerned about their social image & status. In order to impress others & to look good so that others feel positive about them they opt impulsive buying. Many a times to lighten their mood buyers buy in a impulsive manner. Impulsive buyers are not much concerned about the results of their spending pattern. Apart from all these price also is a contributing factor. A number of people go for impulsive purchasing just due to the reason it was on discount. Temptations like stock clearances or offers for premium customers also promote impulsive buying.

Objectives:

- ✓ To know how consumers traditional planned shopping behaviour is shifting to impulse buying behaviour.
- ✓ To evaluate the stimuli that trigger impulse buying.
- ✓ To ascertain the extent of impulsive buying behaviour.

Determinants of Impulsive Buying Behaviour: All individual vary from each other in ways of shopping. But there are some psychological elements which are responsible for impulsive buying & are common to all. These psychological factors can be listed as following:

Emotions: Emotions play a vital role in impulsive shopping. Shopkeepers are very well aware of this thing & they hit on this sensitive point. Children are very soft target & can be attracted very easily. Shopping helps buyer in fighting insecurity & give them feeling of completeness.

Addiction: With the changing social scenario shopping is developing as an addiction. People want latest stuff for themselves & family. Social media is encouraging shopping by making people aware of the latest trend & various offers thus evolving shopping as an addiction.

Stress: Many people feel that by doing shopping, they will feel happy but they are not aware of the fact that this pleasure is timely & will lose quality with time. By doing impulsive shopping consumers carry illusion that it will be a stress buster but after reaching home they feel guilty & start thinking that they should not have done particular shopping.

Age: Age is one of the imperative factors that influence impulsive shopping. It has been observed that younger shoppers are more impulsive as compared to elder ones. However in developing countries like Pakistan where younger generation due to lack of independent source of income is very much dependent on their family no such trend can be observed.

Gender: Gender is another important cause for impulse buying behaviour, Some studies declare women as more impulsive as compared to men in buying. While some other studies find men to be more impulsive than women as females carefully plan their purchases.

Income: People belonging to high income group having high disposable income can be assumed to be more impulsive buyer as compared to people with low disposable income.

Culture: The individualism-collectivism dimension of culture is the most imperative cultural factors concerning the issue of impulse buying behaviour. In collectivism model individuals consider themselves as a part of group while in individualism, person consider him / her as autonomous. In case where the individual consider oneself independent there exist greater level of freedom & liberty which may influence impulsive buying as compared to one who is bounded by some group may be friends or family.

Drawbacks of Impulsive Shopping:

No control on budget: Impulsive shopping is done without prior thought & without planning. Acting on impulse many people do shopping but afterwards regret doing so. Impulsive shopping spoils budget & divert funds to none or less utility items.

Wrong Decisions: In normal shopping any goods or product is purchased after proper evaluation of its quality & features, while in case of impulsive buying no pre thought is done. Many a times shoppers purchase goods or products without bargaining or evaluating & later regret for non-utilization of funds.

Hampers Rational Thinking: Impulsive shopping makes buyer behave irrational. Impulsive shopping gradually hampers rational thinking & reasoning capabilities which is expected from every buyer. As a result of impulsive thinking shoppers gradually start trusting people easily & are often cheated by others.

Wastage: Impulsive buying is mainly based on visual appeal. For impulsive buyers seeing is buying. Even though they have not much utility for the product still they buy it, say for example even though a person has crockery at home but on seeing an attractive one he/she buys it.

How to Avoid Impulsive Shopping:

- ✓ One shall plan his/her shopping to make shopping economic & budget friendly.
- ✓ List of necessary item shall be made & buyer shall stick to that only.
- ✓ Visual displays at the shops are too tempting, one shall avoid such temptations.
- ✓ Children who are the soft target shall be avoided to be accompanied during shopping.

Review of Literature:

Obeidat, (1989) in his study he states that women's impulsivity and its possible effects on their consumption patterns in the marketplace. The sample of this study was 328 women. They selected various Jordanian cities and towns according certain conditions. In this study they used questionnaire, for this they choose different age of women. Women's impulsivity will vary according educational attainment, their occupational status, age categories and divorced women. Finally, women's impulsivity increases as women become older and older.

Park, Kim, & Forney, (2006) the purpose of this study was to determine the positive emotion, casual relationship among fashion enrollment, hedonic consumption tendency, and fashion-oriented impulse buying in shopping context. They used questionnaire method and get response from 217 college students. Model they used in their structural equation was correlation matrix and estimated LISREL was 8.53 which were maximum in likelihood. In this fashion involvement and positive emotion would effected positively on consumers fashion-oriented impulse behaviour of buying also fashion involvement got greatest effect. Hedonic tendency of consumption had an important mediator in influential fashion- oriented of impulse buying.

Hung, (2008) in his study he focused on female consumer impulse buying behaviour in the environment of e-commerce. In this research collected the demographic data. In this survey method will be used or Cronbach Alpha is used. In this they use five factors like promotion and advertisement, environment stimuli,

situational factors and customer impulse buying tendencies and product related factors are included. Except promotion and advertising all factors contributes to influence the behaviour of female online impulse buying.

Tendai & Crispen, (2009) in their study they investigated the influence of in-store shopping environment on impulsive buying among consumer. He used survey research method. A total of 320 shoppers conveniently sampled at selected shopping mall in King Williams town, South Africa, served as a sample. The result of the study had shown that coupons and vouchers, store display, advertisements and promotions, behaviours of shop staff as well as price were the only significant determinants of impulse buying among the 9 factors investigated.

Karbasivar & Yarahmadi, (2011) was concluded that to find the variables/factors that effects customer impulse buying behaviour. He used survey research method. The sample size for this research was 275, collected from Abdan, Iran. To check the reliability in data, he used chronbach Alpha. To test the variables he developed a Structure Equation Modeling (SEM) with Linear Structural Relationships (LISREL). Results showed that impulse buying behaviour was more affected by cash discount and window display as compared to credit card and free products.

Dipta Dharmesti, (2012) identified the role of consumption as a mediator of external stimuli and mood to online impulse buying decision, and the role of frequency of the online shopping as the mediator consumption impulse-online impulsive buying decision relationship. The relationship between consumption impulse and online impulse buying decision is moderated by frequency of online shopping.

Research Methodology:

Survey Method has been followed for the study. Both primary and secondary source of data were used. Well-structured questionnaire was designed to elicit necessary data and details. The secondary data were collected from the books, journals, web portals, etc.

Primary Data: Out of 100 questionnaires, only 75 were received as completely filled have been used in the Present study. The questionnaires were directly given to respondents. The instructions were clearly given in order to avoid biasness in the responses. It was made sure, in this study, that the data collected through questionnaires were complete in all respects.

Secondary Data: Secondary data was obtained through the text books, journals, periodicals, internet, and so on.

Statistics Tools: As the question generate direct information the data were analyzed using Statistical tools such as, Percentage Analysis, ANOVA, Mean Score, Mean Rank etc...

Hypothesis Framework:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between educational qualification and external stimuli's.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Demographic Profile of the Respondents:

Demographic Variable		No. of Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Gender	Male	31	41.3	41.3
	Female	44	58.7	100
	Total	75	100	
Age	Below 19 years	8	10.7	10.7
	20-39 years	65	86.7	97.3
	40-59 years	2	2.7	100.0
	Total	75	100	
Educational Qualification	School level	3	4	4.0
	Graduates	55	73.3	77.3
	Post graduates	13	17.3	94.7
	Professionals	4	5.3	100.0
	Total	75	100	
Marital Status	Single	60	80	80.0
	married	15	20	100.0
	Total	75	100	
Occupation	Student	20	26.7	26.7
	Employee	32	42.7	69.3
	Businessman	6	8	77.3
	Professionals	8	10.7	88.0
	Home maker	9	12	100.0
	Total	75	100	
Place of Residence	Urban	20	26.7	26.7
	Rural	55	73.3	100.0
	Total	75	100	
Monthly	Below Rs.15,000	46	61.3	61.3

Family Income	Rs.15,000-Rs.25,000	24	32	93.3
	Rs.25,000-Rs 30,000	5	6.7	100.0
	Above 30,000	0	100	
	Total	75		
Family Size	2 members	4	5.3	
	3 - 4 members	69	92	5.3
	5 - 6 members	2	2.7	97.3
	Above 6 members	0	0	100.0
	Total	75	100	

Source: Primary Data

The inferences of the above table are given below:

- ✓ In the case of gender, out of 75 respondents, 58.7% of the respondents were female and the remaining 41.3% were male.
- ✓ Out of 75 respondents, majority 86.7% of the respondents were under the age group of 20-39 years, 10.7% of the respondents were under the age group of below 19 years, 2.7% of the respondents were under the age group of 40-59 years.
- ✓ With regard to the educational qualification of the respondents, Out of 75 respondents, 73.3% of the respondents were completed under graduation, 17.3% of them were completed their post graduates, 5.3% of them were professionals, 4% of the respondents were under school level education.
- ✓ Out of total respondents, 80% were single and the remaining 20% were married.
- ✓ Among five occupation group of the respondents, 42.7% of the respondents were employees, 26.7% of the respondents were students, 12% of the respondents were homemakers, 10.7% of respondents were professionals and 8% of the respondents were businessman.
- ✓ 73.3% of the respondents were living in rural area and remaining 26.7% of the respondents were living in urban area.
- ✓ Out of total 75 respondents monthly income, 61.3% of the respondents family income were below Rs. 15,000 per month, 32% of the respondents family income were earning between Rs.15,000-Rs.25,000 per month, 5% of the respondents family income were earning between Rs. 25,000-Rs.30,000 per month.
- ✓ In the case of number of members in the respondents family, out of total 75 respondents, 92% of the respondents were having 3-4 members in their family, 5.3% of the respondents were having 2 members in their family, 2.7% of the respondents were having 5-6 members in their family.

ANOVA Relationship between Educational Qualification and External Stimuli's:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between educational qualification and external stimuli's.

External Stimuli's		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Personalized Attention	Between Groups	1.135	3	0.378	1.491	0.224
	Within Groups	18.012	71	0.254		
	Total	19.147	75			
Price	Between Groups	4.611	3	1.537	8.038	0.000
	Within Groups	13.576	71	0.191		
	Total	18.187	75			
Product Uniqueness	Between Groups	1.769	3	0.590	1.835	0.149
	Within Groups	22.818	71	0.321		
	Total	24.587	75			
Staff Etiquette	Between Groups	1.191	3	0.397	1.128	0.344
	Within Groups	24.995	71	0.352		
	Total	26.187	75			
Quality	Between Groups	2.304	3	0.768	.855	0.469
	Within Groups	63.776	71	0.898		
	Total	66.080	75			
Product Display	Between Groups	6.074	3	2.025	2.555	0.062
	Within Groups	56.272	71	0.793		
	Total	62.347	75			

Advertisement	Between Groups	2.375	3	0.792	1.090	0.359
	Within Groups	51.572	71	0.726		
	Total	53.947	75			
Promotional Scheme	Between Groups	4.611	3	1.537	8.038	0.000
	Within Groups	13.576	71	0.191		
	Total	18.187	75			

Source: Primary Data

The numerated value is less than the level of significance (i.e, 0.05) which denotes that there is a significant relationship between educational qualification and external stimuli's like price (0.000), product display (0.062), promotional scheme (0.000). Therefore, null hypothesis is rejected, whereas the statement is accepted when the calculated value is greater than the table value which denotes that there was no significant relationship between the educational qualification and external stimuli's like personalized attention (0.224), Product uniqueness (0.149), Staff etiquette (0.344), Quality (0.469), Advertisement (0.359). Hence, the framed hypothesis is accepted.

Mean Score Analysis:

Extent of Impulsive Buying Behaviour:

Attributes	Mean Score Value
Always plan before purchase	1.23
I often buy things without thinking	2.03
I usually find it great pleasure in shopping	1.45
I will buy when I have more money	1.59
When I shop, I tend to impulse buy	1.84
I buy products, if I get any free coupons	1.91
Shopping is fun	1.25

Source: Primary Data

According to the results of mean score analysis. The mean scores are ranked according to their values. It was clearly elucidated from the above table, I often buy things without thinking is the main factor which is preferred first by the consumers with the mean score of 2.03, followed by I buy products, if I get any free coupons with the mean score of 1.91, When I shop, I tend to impulse buy with the mean score of 1.84, I will buy when I have more money with the mean score of 1.59, I usually find it great pleasure in shopping with the mean score of 1.45, Shopping is fun with the mean score of 1.25, Always plan before purchase with the mean score of 1.23. It was clearly illuminated that the first rank was given to I often buy things without thinking and last rank was given to Always plan before purchase.

Mean Rank:

Mean Rank on factors that Influence in Impulse Buying Behaviour of Consumers:

S.No	Particulars	Average Mean	Rank
1	Seasonal Offers	5.74	7
2	Packaging	5.35	6
3	Free Gifts	2.89	2
4	Credit Sales	4.40	5
5	Curiosity	3.03	3
6	Availability	3.77	4
7	Discounts	2.82	1

Source: Primary Data

The above table construed about the mean rank of the factors that influence in impulse buying behaviour of consumers. In this method, the lowest average mean value ranks first and the highest average mean value ranks last. Therefore, first rank was given to Discounts, the second rank was given to Free Gifts, the third rank was given to Curiosity, the fourth rank was given to Availability, the fifth rank was given to Credit Sales, the sixth rank was given to Packaging, the seventh rank was given to Seasonal Offers. It was concluded that Discounts was given first rank and Seasonal Offers was given last rank and the factor with first rank can be taken for decision making process of the study.

Findings:

Percentage Analysis:

Among the 75 respondents, 58.7% of them were female, 86.7% of them were in the age group of 20-39years, 73.3% of the respondents were completed their under graduation, 80% of the respondents were single, 42.7% of the respondents were employees, 61.3% of them had monthly family income below Rs,15000, 73.3% of the respondents were from rural area, 92% of them had 3 to 4 members in their family.

ANOVA:

The calculated value is less than the level of significance (i.e, 0.05) which denotes that there is a significant relationship between educational qualification and external stimuli's like price (0.000), product display (0.062), promotional scheme (0.000). Therefore, null hypothesis is rejected, whereas the statement is accepted when the calculated value is greater than the table value which denotes that there was no significant relationship between the educational qualification and external stimuli's like personalized attention (0.224), Product uniqueness (0.149), Staff etiquette (0.344), Quality (0.469), Advertisement (0.359). Hence, the framed hypothesis is accepted.

Mean Score Analysis:

According to the results of mean score analysis. It was clearly illuminated that the first rank was given to I often buy things without thinking and last rank was given to Always plan before purchase.

Mean Rank:

The data indicates the average mean and the mean rank of the factors that influence in impulse buying behaviour of consumers. It was concluded that Discounts was given first rank and Seasonal Offers was given last rank and the factor with first rank can be taken for decision making process of the study.

Suggestions:

- ✓ The consumers should understand the wants and needs of their family. Impulse buying disrupts the normal decision making models in consumer's brains.
- ✓ The logical sequence of the consumer's actions is replaced with an irrational moment of self gratification. Impulse items appeal to the emotional side of consumers.
- ✓ Some items bought on impulse are not considered functional or necessary in the consumer's live. Preventing impulse buying involves techniques such as setting budgets before shopping and taking time out before the purchase is made.

Conclusion:

Through its social, cultural, political, legal, economic and even technological dimension, the contemporary marketing environment changes traditional behaviour patterns of both males and females. This is followed by economic and sociological explanations regarding the research into external stimuli of consumer behaviour, and their interpersonal relations and communications. The final stage comprises psychological rationales, which are intrinsically internal in character, and is conducted with the aim of comprehending the intra-personal determinants, which powerfully shape consumer behaviour, in interaction with the effect of external factors. From the above studies it can be concluded that Indian customers are most of the time emotionally driven to any product & it has paved the way for retailers to take on various promotional tactics for attracting general mass & converting them in customers. Impulsive buying can be referred as deeply rooted phenomenon in the individual trait of the consumers.

Scope for the Further Study:

- ✓ Further research can be carried out to increase and understanding the concept of consumer behaviour and impulsive buying behaviour of the consumers.
- ✓ Comparative study about impulsive buying and compulsive buying can be conducted in future.
- ✓ Further study can be conducted to find out the outcomes of impulsive habits.

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